

‘Veena’ in the Development of ‘Art and Science’ of Music

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Abstract

‘Veena’, the most ancient stringed instrument of India, has a recorded history dating back to the Rig Vedic age. With Veena as the guiding star, there has been a continuous progress in various concepts of music, conforming to the practices and traditions in vogue from time to time, which can be traced through lakshana granthas from ancient to the modern periods. From Bharatha Muni (2nd Century BC – 2nd Century AD) down to Subbarama Dikshitar (19th Century), we find that the musical phenomena have been explained with the aid of Veena, revealing the importance of the instrument in the development of the art and science of Music.

Keywords : Indian Music, Veena Instrument, Carnatic Music, Indian Musicology, South Indian Music, Ancient String Instrument, Role of Veena, Musicological development.

1. Introduction

From being a melodic accompaniment to that of emerging as a solo instrument, Veena evolved over the centuries in shape, size, strings, frets, manner and technique of play, and in its present form, has become an instrument par excellence of Indian music which represents the cultural ethos of India. Endowed with divinity, it is associated with Gods and Goddesses of Hindu Mythology and referred as one of the three principal instruments mentioned in Vedic literature.

Rightly called the ‘Queen of Instruments’, it is one of the very few ancient instruments to have retained its exalted status in modern times. The Veena had come to dominate musical thought so much that even Vocal music was described as ‘Gatra Veena’ and writers also described the parallels between the strings of the Veena and the frets with the Nadi-s and Chakra-s in the human system.

2. Veena and the Musical Phenomena

The Veena became an instrument used for demonstration and explanation of musical terms as it happens to be the best audio visual medium to comprehend the concepts of music, strengthened by the fact that the note produced by a veena string has its fine tone quality due to rich harmonic overtones and facilitates the production of subtle quarter tone and graces by deflection of strings. Infact, Veena is a complete instrument comprising the factors of Sruti and Laya, with the presence of tala strings in addition to the main playing strings.

Several experiments in the evolution of music theory and practice with regard to the

- i. concept of Sruti-s
- ii. arrangement of Swara-s
- iii. construction and acoustical studies, resulting in the development of a
- iv. systematic approach to the Mela-Raga system
- v. Gamaka-s
- vi. Tanam etc.,

have been done with reference to the Veena, thus portraying its unique significance.

2.1 Sruti-s and Swara-s

Sruti-s and Swara-s are the very pillars on which the edifice of Indian music rests. The concept of Sruti, which is pivotal in the theory of Indian Music, is an ancient one having links from Vedic time. In the history of World music, Indian Music is one of the earliest to use quarter-tones or srutis. The theoretical system formulated to codify the music of the ancient period was the ‘Gramma System’ - a framework in terms of 22 micro-tonal intervals (srutis)

comprising an Octave. Sruti was the unit of measure of svara-s, and the 22 Sruti-s were derived upon the principle of Samvaditva or Consonance and evolved through the Cycles of Fifths (Shadja-Panchama Bhava) and the Cycles of Fourths (Shadja-Madhyama Bhava).

Samvaditva being the keynote of Bharata's system, with the help of an experiment conducted on the Dhruva and Chala Veena, he devised the 22 srutis and explained the Shadja and Madhyama Gramas with proper sruti values. By a practical demonstration known as 'Sarana Chatushtaya', he proved the chatuhshruti interval of notes in the gramas. Sarangadeva and Matanga explained in greater detail than Bharata, the experiment with the Dhruva and Chala Veenas to clarify the Grama concept and Sruti values.

While Bharata's experiment explained swaras in terms of srutis, Sarangadeva's experiment established sruti-s first to position the svara-s. As svara was conceived both as an interval and as a pitch position, Sruti was also thought of both as the least audible interval between two sounds, as well as the sounds themselves which were separated by such an interval. A sthayi was conceived of as the sum total of 22 sruti-s of unequal size. The presence of Srutis is concealed as they are enfolded by Swaras, which assume importance in the formation of Swara variations.

2.2 Swaras and their relationships

Swaras and their relationships have been explained on the basis of the four essential qualities of – Vaditva, Samvaditva, Vivaditva and Anuvaditva. These concepts which have taken shape in the ancient period have been extended upto the mela system of the medieval period. In many of the texts which explained the mela system, the suddha and vikrita swaras were illustrated with the help of Veena-s.

2.3 Veena – Construction and Acoustics

While the ancient period represented the Sruti Veena-s with open strings, the emergence of a new variety of veena with frets is a milestone in the history of Indian Music. It was seen in the medieval period that with the fixing of frets and determining the sound values of the speaking length of the wires, the method of construction of Veenas, tuning of strings, the number of strings and the manner of playing was explained.

The idea of placing frets on the veena is first mentioned in 'Manasollasa' of Somesvara (12th century) but a more detailed description was given in Sangeeta Ratnakara (13th century) with regard to the materials used and also the distance between consecutive frets. The introduction of frets helped in the development of the concept of Raga. The adornment of individual notes through shakes and subtle oscillations of pitch became distinct possibilities with the emergence of the fretted veena. Playing gamakas on veena involved a complicated technique and many varieties of playing these were mentioned by Sarangadeva. This led to rendition of aesthetically excellent musical phrases on the veena.

2.4 Veena – Lending a Systematic approach to Mela-Raga classification

The concept of Raga propounded by Matanga (8-9 centuries) brought about great changes in the techniques of veena playing. Gamaka, the soul of Indian Music, gained importance. Further, the remarkable development that had taken place in the construction of Veena in the medieval period, had made the evolution of new and logical concepts possible. As a consequence, arose the mela system of raga classification, which was definitely related to the fretting of Veenas of those times. The attempt to locate the Swaras on the Veena under fixed frets brought changes in the Swara nomenclature and led to the formulation of new mela systems.

For many centuries ragas were described in terms of Murcchanas and Jatis. Centuries of experimentation and development of music led to an increase in the number of raga-s and this necessitated a proper classification of raga-s. In such a situation, ragas were classified

based on the arrangement of svara-s which had affinity to certain fundamental scales. Thus, the janaka-janya system of classification came into existence during the early medieval period.

The mela at present is understood as the regular and homogeneous arrangement of seven swaras with a uniform ascent and descent characterized by absolute pitches, definable in terms of the Veena frets. By Mela is meant the fretting in instrumental music. Eka raga and Sarva raga mela represent the fretting of veena to suit the playing of one and many ragas respectively. It is probable that the term mela to mean a raga with certain qualifications is derived from the melas of the veena.

The idea of mela prastara or working out the possible number of melas by the use of permutation and combination was also probably inspired by the tana prastara and tala prastaras expounded in great detail in the Sangita Ratnakara and other works. A study of the history of mela prastara from the time of Somanatha, the originator of the scheme of melas as such, down to the period of Govinda(acharya) brings to light the other mela schemes formulated by various lakshanakaras.

2.5 Veena and Gamaka-s

We understand through texts that 'Alankara-s' that adorned the ancient music were the precursors to 'Gamaka-s' of the later period. While Brihaddesi of Matanga (8-9 centuries) gives the first reference to the term 'Gamaka', it is Sangeeta Ratnakara of Sarangadeva (13th Century) which is the first treatise to define 'Gamaka' and enumerate 15 varieties, giving the accurate time value of these gamaka-s.

It is interesting to note that explanation of gamakas has been done with reference to veena in terms of deflection of strings, stress, shake, upward and downward glides on the strings, playing on a fret in three strings etc. Raga Vibodha also explains the 22 varieties of gamakas mentioned in the treatise with reference to their production on Veena. Popularly known Dasavidha gamakas are also explained in terms of Veena.

2.6 Veena and Tanam

The connotation of the term Tanam and the way of its rendering has changed drastically from the ancient period to what it is today. Playing of 'Tanam', the most enthralling component of Manodharma Sangeeta, seems to have evolved from the techniques of Veena. Following certain time measures in using the tala strings, the flow of melody is maintained and the quality of music is enriched by using the tala strings for both rhythm and drone, an exclusive facility featured in the Veena.

3. Conclusion

From the above discussions and analysis, it is clearly evident that through all these conceptualisations, it was Veena that played a very significant role in the establishment of several musical and musicological concepts. Infact, Veena has been the veritable visual aid in comprehensively understanding the nuances and subtleties of Carnatic Music, it being the only instrument comprising all the aspects of Sruti, Laya and Melodic rendition with aesthetics.

References:

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